

1 **TB in patients with advanced HIV.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the whole blood in humans with HIV and in humans with combined
8 tuberculosis and HIV-1 (HIV/TB) infection to describe novel transcriptional features of HIV-TB co-infection
9 in man. Patients with co-infection activated immune receptors *Vsig2* and *Lrrc4*. Innate immune detection
10 reflected co-infection with activation of *Naip* and *Tlr5*. Cells were enriched for *Gpr27* in co-infection and
11 expressed *Fcgr1bp*. *Sod2* was specifically induced in co-infection suggesting differential cellular demands
12 during combined pathogenic insult. We demonstrate here activation of a nuclear factor known as *Gsec*
13 specifically in humans with co-infection.

14 Citations

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1. Bell, L.C. and Noursadeghi, M., 2018. Pathogenesis of HIV-1 and Mycobacterium tuberculosis
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